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FEDORA

Deliverable 6.4

FEDORA Official Video

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FEDORA - Future-oriented Science EDUcation to enhance Responsibility and engagement in the society of Acceleration and uncertainty
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www.fedora-project.eu

Quality assurance

To ensure the quality and correctness of this deliverable, we implied an internal review and validation process. The deliverable was drafted by the work package leader (formicablu). All partners contributed to and reviewed the overall draft. Finally, the semi-final version was submitted to the project coordinator for a final review and validation.

Version	Date	Status	Author	
V0	20/08/2021	Draft	Formicablu A. Troncoso	Creation of the document
V1	28/08/2021	First internal revision	Formicablu E. Tola, F. Conti	Integration of the document
V2	30/08/2021	Submitted to Coordinator		
V3	31/08/2021	Submitted on the Portal		

Disclaimer

This deliverable contains original, unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. It builds upon the experience of the team and related work published on this topic.

Acknowledgement of previously published material and others' work has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both.

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1. SUMMARY

Deliverable 6.4 “FEDORA Project Official Video” presents the steps of the process that led to the creation of a short video that communicates the project’s main goals and its approaches.

Building upon FEDORA’s Branding Guidelines and FEDORA’s objectives, the video intends to be a communication tool to be used by the Consortium in diverse communication events and opportunities.

This document is the fourth deliverable of Work Package 6, “Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation”, led by formicablu.

2. PROJECT OVERVIEW

FEDORA will develop a future-oriented model to enable formal and informal science education to equip the young with thinking, foresight and action competence skills needed to grapple with societal challenges.

In particular, the project aims to address three forms of misalignment that emerge from the difficulties of the educational systems to keep the pace of societal changes: a) the clash between, on the one hand, the vertical and hyper-specialised organisation of teaching in disciplines and, on the other, the inter-multi-transdisciplinary, multi-actor and open character of the new modus operandi of R&I; b) the mismatch between the formalised and exclusive languages used in schools and the needs for new languages to enhance imagination and the capacity to talk about the contemporary challenges; c) the clash between the a-temporal or historically oriented teaching approaches and the need to support the young to construct visions of the future that empower actions in the present.

These forms of misalignment represent blind spots for science education that FEDORA will explore through a multi-layer (institutional, conceptual, cultural) research approach, articulated structures of actions and a multiform set of research methodologies. The actions and results will feed into recommendations for anticipatory policies aimed to mobilise visionary attitudes on open-schooling and orient concrete institutional transformations to nurture, in secondary school students, a new sense of trust and desire needed to support an aware, responsible and sustainable participation in science-related societal issues.

FEDORA's main objective is to align science education with the fast-changing society and with R&I. This overarching goal is articulated into four general objectives, summarised here:

1. Contribute to aligning the traditional educational institutions with the ways R&I is produced;
2. Contribute to aligning (informal, non-formal and formal) science education with the society of acceleration;
3. Contribute to "futurising" science education;

4. Support the young generation to increase their personal and public engagement in science, their employability and hope, trust, desire, visionary and proactive moods in this accelerated, multi-velocity, complex and uncertain society.

3. INTRODUCTION AND TASKS

Deliverable D6.4 is part of Task 6.4: “**Multimedia Production**”, Work Package 6 “Behind the scenes: communicating and disseminating FEDORA in its making”. It is closely connected to Deliverable 6.1 “**Communication and Dissemination Plan**” and D6.3, “**FEDORA visual identity and project website**” and serves its objectives, which comprise the following:

1. Ensure effective communication and dissemination of the project: internal communication and outreach;
2. Provide partners with a common strategy, tools and guidelines that facilitate their participation and the optimal implementation of the plan;
3. Identify key messages that resonate with different target audiences;
4. Establish meaningful evaluation criteria for monitoring the effectiveness of the plan;
5. Describe ways of collaborating with other related EU projects.

The impact and reach of the current communication multimedia product, FEDORA’s video, will be enriched by D6.5 FEDORA Podcast (M24) and D6.6 Policy brief (M24).

4. DEVELOPING FEDORA'S OFFICIAL VIDEO SCRIPT

The process for developing ideas and executing the production of this video are summarised in the following steps:

- Discovering key messages in the project proposal: a) Slogan b) Main problem to be solved c) Mission, vision and methods
- Aesthetics: deciding on the look and feel
- Drafting some ideas and selecting the ones that reflect in a more compelling way the key messages
- Final touches

These are the key messages that we selected from the proposal and that guides the string of ideas in the video:

- SLOGAN: Future-oriented Science Education to enhance Responsibility and Engagement in the society of acceleration and uncertainty
- PROBLEM: "We can't keep navigating a fast-paced changing present time with the old maps that have been accompanying us as society"
- MISSION: Regenerating science learning (formal and informal education).

More specifically:

- To deal with complexity and uncertainty in the society of acceleration
- We propose a future-model based on active hope, collaboration, foresight and creative thinking
 - a) VISION AND METHODS: Fixing 3 misalignments
- Aligning science teaching/learning in formal contexts with the *modus operandi* of R&I: Vertical and hyper- specialised organization of teaching in disciplines VS the inter-multi-transdisciplinary, the character of innovation, research and science.
- Exploring new languages, narratives and arts in science education: Formalized and exclusive languages used in schools VS the needs for new languages to enhance imagination and the capacity to talk about the contemporary challenges
- Futurizing science education: A-temporal or historically oriented teaching approaches VS the need to support the young to construct visions of the future that empower actions in the present.

5. THE FINAL VIDEO SCRIPT

Based on the key messages, the written proposal and the development of the project, the following script was written and recorded by a professional voice presenter:

How are we learning and experiencing science today, especially at school? Using a metaphor is like learning geography from an old map and finding our way in today's world.

We are facing a fast-changing present time; we live in what the sociologist Hartmut Rosa calls "the society of acceleration", but our educational systems often remain rigid and do not appear able to keep the pace of change. FEDORA is an EU project aimed at regenerating the ecosystem of science learning in both formal and informal environments. We acknowledge three main dissonances that can be brought into a nicer piece! We see a clash between, on the one hand, the vertical and hyper- specialised organisation of teaching in disciplines and, on the other, the inter-multi-transdisciplinary character of innovation and the efforts to make research and science an open and collaborative space. We see a second mismatch between the formalised and exclusive languages used in schools and the need for new languages to enhance imagination and the capacity to talk about contemporary challenges. And we also identify a discrepancy between the a-temporal or historically oriented teaching approaches and the need to support the young to construct visions of the future that empower actions in the present.

Our research will be based on literature in science education research and corpora of texts produced by hundreds of students and critical informants' surveys. While involving experts from diverse fields in our working groups, the outcoming results of our studies will inform our approaches for action. They will tailor recommendations for open-schooling networks, instruction designers, policymakers and policy institutions in a way that they can implement changes step-by-step.

Keep informed and engaged!

The visuals and this audio will be followed by the website address, hashtags #fedoraproject and #openschooling on Twitter, the partners' names and their logos: University of Bologna, University of Helsinki, Kaunas University of Technology, University of Oxford, FormicaBlu and Teach the Future.

6. THE LINK TO THE FINAL VIDEO

FEDORA - Future-oriented Science EDucation to enhance Responsibility and engagement in the society of Acceleration and uncertainty This project received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation program under Grant Agreement n° 872841 www.fedora-project.eu

The final video is available both on Fedora's website and on formicablu's YouTube channel.

Here is the link to the FEDORA website and the post launching the video:

<https://www.fedora-project.eu/fedora-launches-short-video-about-the-project-enjoy/>

And here the link to Formicablu's YouTube channel for easy sharing:

Here is the link to the YouTube channel:

<https://youtu.be/W0muUdSTytI>

